

Indigenous Community Partners

Inuit in Attu and Aasiaat

Inupiaq and Yupiaq in Unalakleet

Gwich'in Nation in Tsiigehtchic

Skolt Sámi in the Näättämö River Basin

Tahltan Nation in Dease Lake Traditional

knowledge communities from Faroe Islands

Partner Organizations

www.arcticpassion.eu

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ARCTIC PASSION

Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems: Implementing Observations for Societal Needs

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In the Arctic, human-induced planetary warming leads to faster changes than anywhere else on our planet. These changes have environmental, societal, and economic impacts, locally and far beyond the Arctic. A sustainable, accessible observing system is needed, tailored to the diverse needs of users, ranging from local inhabitants to academia, through to industry and decision-makers.

Free and open access to the best-available information and services empowers communities, governments, and others to develop evidence-based, societal decisions. As the Arctic changes, the demand for improved access to more reliable and diverse observational data streams and services will proceed. Access to the latest environmental observations strengthens the decisions we make for a safe and prosperous Arctic.

The project

Arctic PASSION aims to improve the situation by co-creating in international collaboration, including Indigenous and local communities, an integrated pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS) that can continuously provide unrestricted, high quality, science-based Earth observation information tuned to address the urgent needs of people living and acting in the Arctic and have relevance to European and global societies.

Co-creating services

To excel in these difficult times communities, industry and governments need timely and unrestricted access to essential information services. But not all such services are available, or easily accessible to non-specialists. Following priorities established by Arctic Council, its Working Groups, the Arctic Science Ministerials, and the Arctic Observing Summit, we will co-create eight Pilot Services with local and Indigenous communities and other Arctic actors, data providers and end-users.

Our services

1. Event database of oral histories, Indigenous and Local Knowledge
2. Integrated wildfire risk management
3. Local atmospheric pollution forecast
4. Improved shipping safety
5. Marine noise pollution & its impacts
6. Lake ice service for climate & safety
7. Pan-Arctic permafrost service
8. Overall state of the Arctic environment products and services.

Project Goals

- Support a 'smart Arctic Observing System' through model-based impact assessments
- Produce innovative user-driven Arctic EuroGEO pilot services
- Support coherent policy and decision-making
- Co-develop a more adaptive and complete, integrated and sustainable pan-AOSS
- Connect the pan-AOSS to society through communication, dissemination and engagement

